

Flood Detection and Monitoring System in Otuoke Community using IOT

Adebayo Adeniyi D.

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering
Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

aadeniyiadebayo@gmail.com

&

Ifeagwu Emmanuel N.

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering
Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

ifeagwuemma@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

As Otuoke community constantly conflicts for a proficient flood observing framework. flood anticipating and the giving of flood alerts are powerful approaches to decrease loss. The proposed framework will be productive in light of the fact that it has better coordination of checking, correspondence and transmission advancements which is versatile to foundation condition. The proposed article will display the data of the water level measured on LCD. This article can be very helpful to the Meteorological Department to continuously monitor the dams and river beds water level. This article is cost-effective, flexible and productive in Otuoke. The Otuoke neighborhood is presented with an innovative Internet of Things-based flood detection and monitoring system by this research. The report discusses the urgent need for a proactive strategy to counteract the growing threats that the region's floods offer. The system utilizes a multi-tiered strategy that involves real-time data collecting, processing, and distribution by leveraging sensor networks and Internet of Things devices. By deploying sensors in strategic locations, the system continuously monitors environmental characteristics that are susceptible to flooding and water levels. Advanced analytics are used to process the gathered data, making it easier to create early warning systems and prediction models. The system's ability to furnish stakeholders and residents with prompt alerts and actionable information guarantees a prompt and efficient response, therefore reducing the adverse effects of floods on the community. The results of this study provide a scalable model for flood control in other vulnerable areas in addition to aiding in the preservation of Otuoke.

Key words: Internet of Things, Flood Disaster, Sensors, Mangroves, Fresh Waters, Weather.

INTRODUCTION

The occurrence of flood disasters consistently inflicts damage upon human populations, resulting in both material losses and casualties. Additionally, these events have the potential to induce permanent or temporary alterations to the environment. Floods are a consequence of severe meteorological conditions characterised by intense precipitation, leading to an excess of water on the land and a noticeable increase in river water levels.

Floods are a consequence of severe weather patterns that lead to intense precipitation, resulting in a significant accumulation of water on land. This is often characterised by a notable increase in the water level of rivers. Nigeria is a nation characterised by substantial precipitation levels, which have the potential to result in the occurrence of flooding events. The prevalence of floods remains a significant concern in many regions, particularly those in close proximity to riverbanks. The rainy seasons in Nigeria are observed annually between the months of March and September. According to Ologunorisa and Tersoo (2006), the initial occurrence of rainfall in the region often transpires in the month of March, followed by a complete onset in April, and concludes in October annually. Additionally, November has sporadic showers, which mark the transition into the dry season accompanied by the customary Harmattan winds.

In Nigeria, floods manifest in three primary forms: coastal, riverine, and urban flooding. Coastal flooding is observed in areas characterised by a relatively low elevation, encompassing mangroves and freshwater wetlands that are situated along the coastline. River floods are a natural phenomenon that transpire inside the floodplains of expansive rivers, characterised by the occurrence of very damaging torrents. metropolitan flooding is a phenomenon that takes place inside metropolitan areas, particularly on level terrains, when surface drainage is either insufficient or obstructed due to garbage accumulation (Folorunsho and Awosika, 2001). Dams are considered to be significant human constructs within the hydrological cycle, designed to impound water in reservoirs during periods of high flow. The primary objective is to utilise this stored water to fulfil human water requirements during periods of insufficient natural flows (Acreman et al., 2000). Nevertheless, the efficacy of dams in benefiting human society has been subject to scrutiny in light of failures that have been linked to catastrophic floods. This is exemplified by the flood incident that occurred as a consequence of the dam's destruction in 'Eleiyele, situated in the upper reaches of the Ona River in the North Ibadan Government Area, during a period of intense rainfall on August 26, 2011 (Agbola, Ajayi, Taiwo & Wahab, 2012). Furthermore, the relocation of more than one thousand individuals in the Ogun River catchment area during October 2010, as well as the inundation of Mile 12 in Lagos State, have been ascribed to the abrupt discharge of water from the Ogun River watershed.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Flooding is a natural phenomenon characterised by the submergence of substantial land areas due to the accumulation of river or rains. It may also denote a transient elevation in the water level, as

observed in a river, lake, or coastal area, resulting in a temporary overflow of water into ordinarily arid terrain.

Frequent instances of flooding are observed in arid regions that experience a sudden inundation of water. The phenomenon of flooding might manifest abruptly and afterwards subside rapidly. The drainage process has a prolonged duration. Flood events can occur sporadically, exhibiting fluctuations in magnitude, duration, and spatial extent. During a flood event, water is observed to move from areas of higher elevation to lower lying areas. Consequently, low-lying regions may experience rapid inundation before to the water's ascent to elevated terrain.

Fig 2.1: flood flow

2.2 Types of floods in Nigeria

2.2.1 Flash flooding

A flash flood is a transient inundation event that typically occurs within a timeframe of two to six hours following the onset of a concentrated precipitation episode. The occurrence of flash floods may be observed in Figure 3. This phenomenon has resemblance to a rapid increase in river water levels, beyond the typical depths of the river. The occurrence is more probable in the vicinity of the river. The occurrence of thunderstorms in specific locations might potentially lead to the simultaneous manifestation of flash floods. Nevertheless, the probability of flash flooding decreases when storms move at a faster pace due to the dispersion of rainfall across a wider geographical area. under the absence of precipitation, the

occurrence of rainfall remains a possibility under several operational scenarios, such as instances following the failure of levees or dams, or subsequent to the abrupt release of water due to debris.

2.2.2 River Flooding

When a river or stream attains flood stage, it has the potential to undergo flooding, resulting in the elevation of water levels and the subsequent overflow of the river's banks. The occurrence of river flooding due to precipitation is contingent upon several factors, including the geographical location, the duration required for rainfall to collect, the saturation level of the local land, and the characteristics of the surrounding topography in proximity to the river system. In the context of a vast and flat floodplain, a river or stream has the potential to induce a persistent flood, characterised by prolonged inundation that does not subside for considerable durations. Flood occurrences are particularly prevalent in the proximate low-lying regions adjacent to rivers.

2.3 Floor Monitoring and Warning Technologies

Two often deployed flood systems are the flood monitoring and warning system, as well as the flood monitoring system alone. In this paper, Section 2.3.1 will provide a comprehensive description of the flood monitoring and warning system, whereas Section 2.3.2 will focus solely on the flood monitoring system without the inclusion of a warning system. This project is classified under the scope outlined in Section 2.3.1, however it employs a distinct methodology for alerting through the use of the SMS system.

The subsequent sections present a comprehensive review of the currently used technology utilised in flood monitoring and warning systems, as well as flood monitoring systems.

2.3.1 Flood Monitoring and Warning System

The implementation of a flood monitoring and warning system that utilises real-time sensors is considered to be an effective method for controlling and mitigating the impacts of floods. This technology not only facilitates the monitoring of flood occurrences but also incorporates warning or alert mechanisms to effectively notify individuals. The use of several strategies, including but not limited to monitoring, forecasting, modelling, and assessment of water levels, can effectively mitigate the economic and societal impacts stemming from flooding incidents. According to E. Basha (year), one method for evaluating flood systems involves the use of a wireless sensor and a web-based decision support system. This approach enables the monitoring, regulating, alleviating, and assessment of natural catastrophes, with a specific focus on flood disasters. The implementation of a monitoring and flood warning system is of utmost importance, as it necessitates both dependability and accurate information. The use of sensor networks is a prevalent approach in detecting fluctuations in water levels and air temperatures. The sensor network utilised in this particular scenario consists of a pressure sensor, a temperature sensor, and a rain sensor. The study involves the deployment of sensor nodes on a tree located near a river in order to monitor the water level and air temperature within the river.

Data collection occurs at regular intervals of 5 minutes, and the collected information is then communicated to a base station over GPRS networks.

A constraint inside the system is the limited range of each sensor node, which restricts the distance it can cover. Additionally, these sensor nodes operate at a predetermined frequency. In the scope of the experiment, it was seen that each sensor node operated at a frequency of 144MHz. Additionally, it was found that the communication range of these nodes extended up to a distance of 25km. In the context of field testing, the deployment of a substantial number of sensor nodes is necessary to provide efficient communication and minimise signal attenuation. Every individual sensor node is required to transmit the updated status of the river water to the central base station.

Figure 2.2: Sensor Network consisting of four nodes.

Within the domain of wireless sensor networks, a diverse array of sensors are employed, including but not limited to the Honeywell pressure sensor, instrumentation amplifier, and computation electronic. In the study conducted by Castillo-Effer (2014), the use of three distinct categories of sensor nodes was observed. The first sensor in question is a hydrological sensor, which is utilised for the purpose of monitoring both water level and water flow. The second sensor is a meteorological sensor node utilised for the purpose of monitoring various environmental parameters such as light intensity, temperature, humidity levels, barometric pressure, wind pressure, and wind speed. The third sensor node functions as a detecting region for landslides, hence being exposed to the associated threat.

2.4 Flood Monitoring and Alert System Past Technology

Numerous scholarly publications have been dedicated to the study of flood monitoring and alerting systems. The majority of the systems employed either distant or local sensing data in order to observe and forecast flood events.

2.4.1 Remote Sensing Data

Satellite remote sensing technology can be utilised as a means of detecting an impending flood. A satellite is a celestial body that orbits the Earth and has the capability to see and record alterations in the state or configuration of the Earth's surface within a specific region many times during the day. The parameters monitored by the satellite remote sensor include soil moisture, surface water body fluctuations, and rainfall information. In order to enhance flood prediction capabilities, weather monitoring, wide-range imagery, and high spatial and temporal resolution are incorporated. The utilisation of satellite remote sensing data enables the prediction of floods through the process of comparing real-time data images with normalised images. The efficacy of this approach is contingent upon the specific characteristics of the satellite system, including the incidence angle, polarisation effects, spatial resolution, and wavelength.

The flood monitoring system plays a vital role in safeguarding communities who are vulnerable to the impacts of flood disasters. The expeditious and precise transfer or delivery of data and information is vital to ensure the effective transmission of this system to the designated recipient. The individual will do an analysis of the system's output and disseminate the projected information to the inhabitants.

2.4.2 Local Sensing Data or Telemetry

Embedded system technology is utilised in local sensing data or telemetry systems to apply the mechanism inside the given context. The topic of embedded systems has gained significant attention in the contemporary electronic industry. The increasing rate of expansion and widespread use of embedded systems on a global scale have contributed to their growing popularity.

Local sensing data or Telemetry system consists of three major parts

1. Sensing
2. Data processing and transmission
3. Application

Sensor Network

The sensor is a fundamental component of Wireless Sensor Networking (WSN) that is responsible for detecting and monitoring the surrounding environment. The careful consideration of sensor choice is crucial for a system in order to guarantee the precision and reliability of the output. There are some factors that necessitate monitoring in order to facilitate flood monitoring and alarm systems.

The parameters are:

- **Hydrological:** The hydrological sensor is employed to measure the water level and the velocity or flow of river water. The sensor has been positioned adjacent to the riverbank..
- **Metrological:** The sensor employed for meteorological purposes is utilised to measure many environmental parameters, including light intensity, ambient temperature, surrounding humidity, barometric pressure, wind direction, and wind speed.
- **Landslide:** The sensor employed for assessing soil moisture levels and the geophone device. The installation of this particular sensor is conducted in the vicinity of the mountainous region surrounding the river.

In order to obtain precise data analysis, it is imperative that the sensors be positioned strategically. Furthermore, it is imperative that the sensors or system deployed in the river be designed to withstand the adverse weather conditions, particularly the monsoon seasons prevalent in the region. In certain instances, a protective coating and moisture-resistant layer are employed to mitigate the risk of system failure.

One of the primary difficulties associated with this approach is in the gathering of data directly from the river. Moreover, the river exhibits a deficiency in terms of power supply and communication infrastructure. This element poses challenges to the practical implementation of the flood monitoring and alarm system.

The accuracy of an environmental sensor network is contingent upon the implementation of a sophisticated system that fulfils the basic requirements for system prediction. This entails ensuring long-term functionality and comprehensive support for all sensors associated with detecting the appearance of flood phenomena. Several instances were documented when the water resulted in the destruction of the mechanism, necessitating its reinstallation.

2.5 Processing and Transmission

The processes of data processing and transmission play a crucial role in facilitating the delivery of data from a node situated at a distant place to the end user. The flood monitoring and alarm system utilises Wireless Sensor Networking (WSN) as its communication technology. Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are extensively employed in flood-prone regions owing to their cost-effectiveness and their ability to provide rapid and precise data transmission. Wireless sensor networks have gained significant popularity and widespread use in several domains of human existence and around the globe. Through the utilisation of this technological advancement, it becomes feasible to effectively monitor and oversee all human actions within the designated timeframe. The table below illustrates many types of Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) communication standards, including 3G, Bluetooth, GSM, ZigBee, and Wi-Fi.

Wireless technology	Range	Data rate	Benefits	Media
3G	Limited	2bits per second	Online application, good for downloading or receiving large files.	Too much memory needed.
Bluetooth	100 meter	700 kilobyte per second	Wireless, low energy consumption.	One to one connection.
GSM	All over the world	9.6 kilobyte per second	Availability, wireless.	Low cost.
<u>ZigBee</u>	100 meter	250 kilobyte per second	Wireless, low cost.	Wireless mesh network.
Wi-Fi	Internet	2.4 gigahertz per second	Wireless, database.	Wireless mesh network.

Table 1 Comparison between wireless networks used

2.6 Flood Reports in Nigeria

According to the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), Nigeria is currently grappling with its most severe floods in the past ten years, resulting in a reported death toll of over 300 individuals in the year 2022. According to the National Emergency Management Agency of Nigeria, the floods that have occurred in 27 out of the 36 states in Nigeria, as well as the capital city, have had an impact on around 500,000 individuals. This includes 100,000 individuals who have been relocated and over 500 individuals who have sustained injuries.

In recent times, there has been a significant surge in the occurrence of climate-related disasters. The primary factors contributing to the occurrence of climate change-induced disasters are alterations in land use patterns, population density, geological characteristics, and geographical positioning. Among the various natural catastrophes triggered by climate change, floods are responsible for around 80% of global fatalities. These events result in an estimated yearly economic loss of \$US 60 billion, causing significant harm to individuals, as well as detrimental effects on agricultural land and infrastructure. The notable alterations in climatic and socio-economic dynamics have led to a rise in the occurrence of flood occurrences throughout time. As a result, officials responsible for disaster management and policy have been compelled to devise methods for assessing regions prone to flooding in order to adopt proactive flood policies.

In recent years, there has been a notable escalation in the frequency and intensity of floods in Nigeria, resulting in significant devastation to human life, infrastructure, and socioeconomic institutions. The occurrence of yearly floods results in significant financial losses, amounting to millions of dollars, in terms of damages to both infrastructure and agricultural land. According to the findings of the Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED), the occurrence

of flooding has resulted in a significant loss of human lives, with a reported death toll exceeding 21,000 individuals, along with substantial economic losses amounting to around US\$17 billion, spanning the period from 1969 to 2020. The September 2020 flood event, characterised by heavy rainfall, river overflow, and flash floods, was brought to attention by the International Federation of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Society (IFRC). This event had a significant impact on a total of 192,594 individuals residing in 22 different states. The consequences of this event included 825 reported injuries, 155 fatalities, and 24,134 individuals being displaced from their homes.

The frequency of flood catastrophes has been seen to be on the rise. This may be attributed to climatic fluctuations, which have resulted in an annual increase in precipitation volume and subsequent increase in runoffs. From a hydrological standpoint, these factors directly contribute to the heightened danger of flooding. The Nigeria Hydrological Services Agency (NIHSA) has identified several factors contributing to flooding in Nigeria, particularly in urban regions. These factors include insufficient drainage infrastructure, inadequate adherence to zoning and planning regulations, and excessive utilisation of vegetated areas that act as natural barriers against floods. The aforementioned situation has resulted in heightened need to develop precise flood risk maps that guarantee sustainable flood risk mitigation and safeguard individuals and infrastructure from detrimental dangers. In order to effectively implement a selected strategy for flood control in Nigeria, it is imperative that governmental authorities, planners, and engineers employ sophisticated tools and techniques to accurately ascertain the specific date, location, and intensity of forthcoming flood events.

A conventional strategy for flood management is the creation of flood hazard maps to identify vulnerable regions susceptible to flooding. Subsequently, suitable solutions are formulated and allocated, which may involve the implementation of structural defences or land use planning. Drawing on the case of Nigeria, it is evident that the absence of comprehensive flood data and the ongoing development of settlements in flood-prone areas have contributed to an escalation in the anticipated yearly losses incurred due to flooding events. Consequently, it has become imperative to evaluate regions susceptible to flooding calamities through the creation of flood susceptibility maps that delineate and categorise the likelihood of flooding at various levels. This approach can facilitate the appropriate prioritisation of areas requiring urgent assistance.

2.7 BAYELSA STATE TOPOGRAPHY

Bayelsa State is characterised by a tropical rainforest ecosystem, whereby over 75% of the region is comprised of water bodies. The topography of the state is predominantly low-lying, extending from Ekeremor to Nembe. The geographical region is predominantly situated at an elevation below that of sea level, characterised by a complex network of winding watercourses and wetlands dominated by mangrove vegetation. The hydrological system in the southern region consists of a complex network of creeks and rivers that ultimately drain into the Atlantic Ocean. Prominent rivers in this system include San Bartholomew, Brass, Nun, Ramos, Santa Barbara, St. Nicholas, Sangana, Fishtown, Ikebiri Creek, Middleton, Digatoro Creek, Pennington, and Dobo. The local flora in this area is predominantly comprised of a mangrove forest. The northern region is

characterised by a dense forest and fertile arable lands suitable for the production of a diverse range of products, including cash crops.

The village of Otuoke is characterised by an average elevation of around 18 metres above sea level. The maximum elevation of the region under consideration is 27 metres, while the minimum height is 7 metres.

Fig 2.3 flood in Otuoke.

METHODOLOGY

The present project use GSM technology, namely the 800L SIM MODULE, in conjunction with an ultrasonic sensor to accurately measure the water level. Subsequently, the collected data is transmitted to the homeowners in order to provide them with timely warnings. Government agencies have the ability to utilise data processing methods that rely on the outcomes of point prediction models in order to initiate early alerts, such as through the Short Message System (SMS), and provide pertinent information to stakeholders who may be at risk of flood exposure. The proposed system use an ultrasonic sensor as a means of detecting and marking the water level in a river. Additionally, a buzzer is incorporated to emit an alarm signal. Furthermore, the system is designed to transmit SMS alerts using a GSM system.

This article will discuss the implementation of an ultrasonic sensor network for the purpose of monitoring water levels in large rivers that are susceptible to floods. Ultrasonic sensors are intended to be installed within containers, such as PVC buckets with a radius of 100mm. The PVC pipe is equipped with three distinct levels that serve as indicators for the water level. Level 1 will be designated as a standard condition, while level 2 will be designated as a state of heightened caution, and level 3 will be designated as a state of significant risk. The levels will be displayed in the table provided below for measuring. Arduino is commonly referred to as node 1, and it is responsible for transmitting data to node 2. Subsequently, node 2 will communicate the data to the base station. Node 2 functions as a GSM system, whereby it processes data in the form of SMS and afterwards transmits it to the inhabitants.

Level	Measurement Between Water Level to Ultrasonic Sensor
NORMAL	>>2 cm
CAUTIOUS	6 to 8 cm
EVACUATION	12Cm

Table 3.1: Label of Level

3.2 MATERIALS

3.2.1 Hardware components

- Arduino Uno
- Breadboard
- RGB LED
- Buzzer
- Ada fruit RGB Backlight LCD16x2
- ESP32CAM
- SIM800Lmodule
- UltrasonicsensorHC-SR04
- Male and female jumper wires
- 9vbattery
- USB–A to B Cable

3.1.2 Software

- Arduino IDE

3.3 Description of Component

Arduino Uno: The controller will have the responsibility of storing and retrieving numerical data that has been collected from the sensors. The Wemos D1 board utilises the ESP-8266EX microcontroller, which features a 32-bit CPU. The device is comprised of eleven digital pins and one analogue pin. The device possesses a flash memory capacity of four megabytes and operates at a voltage of 3.3 volts. The dimensions of the object are 68.6mm by 53.44mm, and it has a mass of 25 grammes. Prior to connecting other devices to the microcontroller, it is crucial to

take into consideration the pin arrangement. Figure 3.1 depicts the Arduino Uno controller.

Fig 3.1: Arduino Uno

Ultrasonic Sensor: Ultrasonic sensors operate based on the principle of sound wave propagation. Electromechanical transducers are capable of converting electrical energy into mechanical energy and vice versa, manifesting as acoustic waves, akin to the functioning principles of RADAR systems. When an ultrasonic sensor perceives an electrical impulse, it emits sound waves periodically over a range of frequencies. When sound waves emitted by the ultrasonic sensor encounter an object, they undergo reflection and return as echo signals. This reflection process generates an electric pulse. The duration between the emission of a signal and the reception of its echo is measured as the distance. Sound-reflecting materials may be recognised regardless of their varying forms and sizes. The requirements of beam spread and target angle have significant importance in the context of ultrasonic sensors. The concept of beam spread refers to the spatial extent within which a circular object may be recognised upon traversing the beam. On the other hand, target angle pertains to the greatest permissible deviation of an obstacle's orientation from the sensor's line of sight, while still ensuring its detection.

The HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor operates at a voltage of 5 volts direct current (DC) and consumes a power of 20 milliamperes (mA). The detection range spans from 0.02 metres to 4 metres, with a range accuracy of 0.002 metres. The utilisation of this particular sensor in the design is justified by its non-contact benefit in comparison to a water-level sensor.

Fig 3.2: ultrasonic sensor

Secure Digital

The Secure Digital (SD) format was created by the SD Card Association as a non-volatile memory card format specifically designed for use in portable electronic devices. The introduction of the technology occurred in 1999, serving as a progression from the multimedia card (MMC). The micro SD reader offers a means of transferring data to and from an SD card. The inclusion of a storage function in embedded devices offers developers increased freedom. The use of this technology encompasses several applications such as audio, video, and graphics, hence enhancing the constrained memory capabilities commonly seen in microcontrollers. The SD card serves as a means of data backup, facilitating the collection and storage of sensor data obtained from both the ultrasonic sensor and the rain sensor module. A distinct file is generated for each individual sensor data. The acquired data is stored in a text format, allowing the four GB memory card to accommodate a substantial amount of information for an extended duration.

The recorded data from both sensors over a 30-second interval consumed about 504 bytes of storage, resulting in an estimated rate of one kilobyte per minute. If the system remains operational for a continuous duration of 24 hours, it will consume a cumulative data volume of 1.4 megabytes. Based on the current rate of usage, it is projected that the memory card will be fully utilised in about 2,875 days. The micro SD reader has the capability to expand memory by a maximum of 32 gigabytes. The compatibility between the micro SD reader and the Wemos D1 microcontroller is established through the utilisation of the standard Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) for communication. The components of this system are the Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) buses, including the Chip Select (CS), Serial Clock (SCK), Master Out Slave In (MOSI), and Master In Slave Out (MISO) signals. The pins have the capability to be programmed in order to facilitate the process of reading data from and writing data to the SD card. The power pins, namely Vcc and GND, are appropriately linked to the corresponding power pins of the Wemos D1 microcontroller. The MISO, MOSI, and SCK SPI buses should be linked to the digital pins D6, D7, and D5, respectively, on the Wemos D1 board. On the other hand, the CS connection can be established using any digital pin available on the Wemos D1.

RGB LED:

An RGB LED refers to a light source that emits white light by the combination of three distinct colours, namely red, green, and blue (RGB). The primary objective of the RGB paradigm is to facilitate the detection, depiction, and exhibition of pictures within electronic systems. The generation of white light can be achieved by the combination of three distinct colours, namely green, red, and blue, or alternatively, by utilising phosphor material. The Light Emitting Diode (LED) is composed of three terminals, internally coloured in Red, Green, and Blue (RGB), as well as a longer lead that functions as either a cathode or an anode.

The construction of Common Anode and Common Cathode LEDs has four terminals. The first terminal is denoted as "R," the second terminal is referred to as "Anode +" or "Cathode -," the third terminal is labelled as "G," and the fourth terminal is designated as "B."

Fig3.3: RGB LED

Breadboard: A breadboard serves as a platform for the construction and experimentation of electronic circuits. This technology enables the placement of components and establishment of connections on a board for circuit creation, eliminating the need for soldering. The apertures included in the breadboard serve the purpose of securing connections by physically grasping components or wires at certain locations, while also establishing electrical connectivity within the board. The high level of user-friendliness and efficiency make this tool ideal for acquiring knowledge and rapidly developing basic circuit designs. Breadboarding is less suitable for the implementation of circuits that are more intricate in nature or operate at higher frequencies. Breadboard circuits are suboptimal for prolonged utilisation compared to circuits constructed on perfboard or PCB. However, they provide the advantage of not requiring soldering (in the case of protoboard) or incurring expenses related to design and manufacture (in the case of PCBs).

Fig 3.4: breadboard

16×2LCD Display

The 16×2 LCD is an electrical gadget utilised for the purpose of displaying messages and data. The acronym LCD stands for Liquid Crystal Display. The nomenclature "16×2 LCD" is derived from the display's configuration of having 16 columns and 2 rows. The display has a total capacity of 32 characters, with each character composed of 5x8 pixel dots. The primary foundation of these displays is predominantly rooted in the use of multi-segment light-emitting diodes. There exists a broad range of display configurations in the market, including 8×1, 8×2, 10×2, 16×1, and others. However, the 16×2 LCD display has significant popularity and widespread usage. The LCD modules discussed below are characterised by their affordability and compatibility with

programming, making them a popular choice for a wide range of do-it-yourself circuits, gadgets, and embedded applications.

Fig 3.5: LCD

Pin on LCD	Description
VSS	Ground pin
VCC	+5vpowersupply
VEE	Pin to change the contract to LCD
RS	Register select :data modem or command mode
RW	Read or write mode
E	Enable LCD
DOB-DB7	Command and data is fed using this pin
LED+	Anode of the Backlight LED
LED	Cathode of the Backlight LED

Table 3.1 Pin Description of 16×2LCD module

Fig 3.6: LCD pin display

ESP32CAM: The microcontroller unit (MCU) under consideration is equipped with a comprehensive set of features, including built-in Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capabilities, enabling its utilisation across a diverse array of applications. The SP32 module has a high level of integration, incorporating various components such as in-built antenna switches, RF balun, power amplifiers, low-noise receive amplifiers, filters, and power management modules. The ESP32 significantly enhances the usefulness and diversity of applications while imposing low restrictions on the Printed Circuit Board (PCB).

Fig 3.7 ESP32CAM

SIM800L MODULE: The SIM800L is a GSM module manufactured by Simocm. It enables microcontrollers to possess GSM capabilities, allowing them to establish connections with the mobile network for the purpose of receiving calls and sending and receiving text messages. Additionally, it facilitates internet connectivity using GPRS, TCP, or IP protocols. An additional benefit lies in the utilisation of pre-existing mobile frequencies by the board, hence enabling its global applicability. The SIM800L is a GSM module that features a serial interface. The device has the capability to both transmit and receive text messages, as well as receive incoming phone calls. Additionally, it has the capability to establish an internet connection and receive FM signals. The SIM800L module may be interfaced with a microcontroller using the serial UART interface. In the provided illustration, it is demonstrated how the module can be linked to an Arduino microcontroller.

Fig 3.8: how sim800l interface with Arduino.

ARDUINO IDE SOFTWARE

The Arduino software, often known as the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE), is an open-source software designed for programming Arduino boards. It is a comprehensive development environment produced by Arduino.cc. This software application facilitates the process of composing and transferring programming code to Arduino microcontroller boards. The system comprises several libraries and a collection of mini-projects as illustrative examples. The

Arduino software (Integrated Development Environment or IDE) exhibits compatibility with several operating systems, including Windows, Linux, and Mac OS X. Moreover, it extends support for programming languages like as C and C++. The Arduino software is user-friendly and accessible for anyone with varying levels of expertise, ranging from novices to advanced users. This platform is utilised for initiating endeavours in electronics programming and robotics, as well as constructing interactive prototypes.

3.3 The role of internet of things in flood detection

The examination and analysis of contemporary events are significantly influenced by the Internet of Things (IoT), leading to a range of ramifications. The concept of the Internet of Things (IoT) is fundamentally rooted in the combination of the terms "Web" (representing a conceptualization of internet usage) and "things" (referring to the organisation and arrangement of physical objects). When combined, these two terms semantically describe the organisation of interconnected variables that may be addressed within established customary practises. The Internet of Things (IoT) was first introduced in the 1980s with the aim of enhancing various remote technologies, including RFID, near field communication, machine-to-machine communication, vehicular-to-vehicular communication, sensors, actuators, and smartphones. These technologies have been strategically implemented in business sectors to implement advanced IoT concepts (Yang et al., 2013; Perumal et al., 2015). During the course of routine framework failure, disk-to-disk communication gradually evolved to restrict itself within a specifically designated framework, whereby certain devices assume the role of relays or gateway administrators. The hand-off administrator is responsible for establishing connectivity between the affected domain and external networks, such as Wi-Fi, Satellite, or cellular networks. The Internet of Things (IoT) is utilised to facilitate the coordination of various devices, ensuring that they effectively communicate with one another in order to accomplish tasks efficiently and impartially within their respective frameworks. Due to the cost-effectiveness of the diverse range of sensors employed, a considerable level of precision is achieved in the data collection process, with the utilisation of hardware with a reasonably high degree of dependability. The use of Internet of Things (IoT) technology is highly sought after, particularly in the context of disaster management initiatives. The process starts with the real-time collecting of data from many sensors, including ultrasonic water flow/level sensors, temperature/humidity sensors, and rain gauges. The entirety of the data is sent to a microcontroller. In the realm of IoT, data analysis of real-time data is conducted in the backend through the utilisation of diverse software components, which may be implemented via cloud/fog or edge computing. Several data mining methods and artificial intelligence/machine learning (ML) approaches are utilised to forecast potential flood hazards by comparing them to predetermined parameters. This information may be disseminated via several channels, including social media platforms, other broadcasting mediums, and the utilisation of warning messages such as the short message service (SMS), thereby facilitating the coordination of evacuation and relief endeavours. Therefore, Internet of Things (IoT) technologies are employed for the purposes of monitoring, tracking, sensing, regulating, and alerting in relation to environmental disasters. Satria et al. (year)

presented a system and conducted experiments to evaluate its performance in the context of real-time flood detection. The project is anticipated to be implemented in a Web-based format, utilising ultrasonic-oriented sensors such as ArduinoUno, wireless routers, and Ethernet shields to effectively measure and transmit precise data on water height, rainfall, and flooding. The collected data will be disseminated to the general public through the internet (Satria et al., 2018). Emerging technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), employ data analytics tools and artificial intelligence (AI) to identify and anticipate potential disasters, hence enabling timely communication to relevant authorities. These technologies have significantly contributed to the preservation of human life, as well as the protection of buildings, monuments, and different forms of infrastructure. Additionally, they have proven useful in locating missing individuals and facilitating effective rescue operations.

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

Flooding is a significant natural calamity in both developing and undeveloped nations, resulting in the loss of human and animal lives as well as property. Floods resulting from seismic activity in oceanic regions, cyclonic storms, precipitation events, and several other natural calamities manifest in numerous regions around the world on an annual basis.

The absence of proper management in the drainage systems of different geographical locations during periods of rainfall results in the occurrence of floods, which unfortunately leads to the loss of numerous human lives. The implementation of an early warning system for floods has the potential to significantly mitigate loss of life. The proposed system utilises technological advancements to detect and monitor rising water levels, enabling timely alerts to be issued in order to facilitate the evacuation of a significant number of individuals.

In this project, a prototype has been developed with the purpose of detecting water levels in various bodies of water such as ponds, dams, rivers, and reservoirs. Upon detection, the prototype is meant to initiate an alarm mechanism by activating a buzzer and sending a text message notification. The present study involves the development of a miniature prototype utilising an Arduino UNO microcontroller, an ultrasonic sensor, a buzzer, an LCD display, LEDs, a SIM800L module, an ESP32CAM module, and various connecting cables.

4.2 Integration of HC-SR04 with Arduino UNO The HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor is a transceiver module utilised for measuring distances. The process of determining distance is conducted by using sound waves. The module operates by emitting an ultrasonic sound wave at a certain frequency. Following the transmission, the receiver engages in a period of waiting for the signal to return subsequent to its interaction with the item. The duration between the emission and reception of a signal is now employed to ascertain the distance of the item. A straightforward formula is employed for the purpose of measuring distance.

Distance = (Speed * Time)/ 2

Here Speed is Speed of sound in the air and Time is the time delay of the ultrasonic wave to strike the object and receive back. The entire formula is divided by 2 as the sound wave travels twice.

Fig 4.1. Circuit diagram of ultrasonic sensor.

Fig 4.2: physical setup of ultrasonic sensor with Arduino.

4.3 Interfacing SIM800L with Arduino

The most important part of the module is the Chip made by SIMCom. Its operating voltage in which works fine ranges from 3.7 V to 4.4 V.

Fig 4.3: circuit diagram

S.N.	ARDUINO	SIM800L
1.	+5 V	VCC
2.	GND	GND
3.	2 (RX)	TXD
4.	3 (TX)	RXD

Table 4.1 Connection table

Fig 4.4 Arduino interfacing with sim800l

4.4 INTERFACING ESP32 CAM WITH ARDUINO

The ESP32-CAM is a very small camera module with the **ESP32-S chip**. The module has an OV2640 camera. It also has several GPIOs to connect peripherals.

The controller is based on a 32-bit CPU with a frequency of up to 240MHz. It has a built-in 520KB SRAM with an external 4M PSRAM. It has a combined 802.11b/g/nWi-Fi + Bluetooth/BLESoC module. It supports image Wi-Fi upload and Embedded Lwip and Free

RTOS.

Fig 4.5 Pin description of ESP32CAM

The most important part of ESP32 CAM is the Camera Module. The Camera Module that you can use is the **OV2640** Camera Module which has a 24 Pin Camera Holder. It has the highest Camera Resolution up to 1600 × 1200.

On the backside, there is an SD card reader which supports SD Card up to 4GB.

The SD card is used for storing images while making images based projects.

Fig 4.4.2: connection between FTDI Module and ESP32 CAMmodule.

4.5 FLOW DIAGRAM

4.6 ARCHITECTURE OF SYSTEM

The system in this project is powered by a battery. The ultrasonic sensor is responsible for transmitting a signal to the GSM shield, which in turn processes the received data in order to send brief messages to areas that have been impacted by floods. When the Ultrasonic Sensor is utilised as an input device. Furthermore, the system incorporates a visual perception system that is universally accessible, enabling users to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the water body. Additionally, an LCD screen is integrated into the system to provide real-time updates on the water level at regular intervals. The system integrates ultrasonic sensors and a GSM shield within a microcontroller.

4.7 EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

The positioning of the ultrasonic sensor and water level will be arranged at distinct vertical positions, ensuring that the transmitter and receiver components are oriented towards the water level. The Arduino UNO microcontroller board is capable of accurately determining the distance between sensors. The liquid crystal display (LCD) will display the measurement of the distance between the objects. Benchmark flood levels are predetermined numbers utilised to establish flood thresholds. When the water level hits these benchmarks, an alarm system consisting of a buzzer programmed to emit both high and low frequency sounds is triggered. Additionally, a liquid crystal display (LCD) is employed to visually display a text-based alert according to the current flood level. The transmission of text messages will be facilitated by the utilisation of the SIM800L module, followed by the subsequent storage of data into an SD card. Additionally, a vision system known as ESP32CAM will be strategically positioned at a data collection site that offers extensive coverage of several water bodies. The camera will be made available to all residents.

MEASUREMENT OF ULTRASONIC SENSOR

LEVEL	DISTANCE	NOTICE	ACTION
SAFE	40cm	----	No need for relocation
LEVEL 1	≥ 20	No flood	No need for relocation
LEVEL 2	≥ 15	Flooded	No need for relocation
LEVEL 3	≤ 10	Critical	Relocation

Percentage error for 20cm

$$\text{Percentage error} = \frac{20.75 \text{ cm} - 20 \text{ cm}}{20 \text{ cm}} \times 100$$

$$= 3.75\%$$

Fig 4.7.1 Physical setup of the project

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